

www.bjisrd.com

Audiovisual Media Types and Their Applications

Alisher Asliddinovich Sabriev

Doctoral Candidate, Research Center for Higher Education Development, Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovations

of the Republic of Uzbekistan

[*alisher.sabriyev95@gmail.com*](mailto:alisher.sabriyev95@gmail.com)

Keywords: *audio component, visual component, simulacra, complete collapse, downfall, augmented reality, education, communication, culture, technologies.*

Introduction

Audiovisual media are tools designed for conveying information and education, recognized as entertainment tools due to their external perception. By combining audio and visual components, they make the process of receiving information more engaging and easier to remember. Audiovisual media enhance the reception of information through two main human senses—hearing and sight. This makes them effective and versatile tools in various fields.

Research Methods. The article primarily uses historical research and text analysis methods. The historical research method is aimed at studying past events, people, phenomena, and processes. This method helps understand specific issues or questions through the collection, analysis, and interpretation of historical data. Initially, information on audiovisual media and their history was collected and studied. Additionally, the genesis and development stages of these media and their integration into various fields were examined through the works of various scholars. Primary and foundational research served as the main sources for the article.

The text analysis method involves the systematic analysis of texts, visual materials, and other types of content. This method studies information by its content and structure to draw precise conclusions. Text

analysis is used in various disciplines, including social sciences, media studies, education, and literary studies. The method helped define research questions and objectives, highlighting crucial aspects for analysis. Selected texts were analyzed for representativeness, ensuring they accurately reflect the general state and characteristics of the research object or population.

Literature Review. Research on audiovisual media is abundant. Foreign scholars have conducted extensive research on audiovisual media and their types. These studies are significant in various fields, including education, communication, culture, and technologies. Canadian scholar Marshall McLuhan's work has greatly influenced global, especially European media development. His theory "The Medium is the Message" [1] explores how audiovisual media impact society. French philosopher and sociologist Jean Baudrillard, known for his media and communication theories, examines the boundaries between reality and virtuality in his work "Simulacra and Simulation" [2]. Baudrillard's concept of "simulacra" describes artificial or fake representations of real things or events. He suggests that in modern society, the lines between reality and artificiality are increasingly blurred. Baudrillard's four-stage model describes the evolution of reality and simulacra:

1. The sign reflects reality (e.g., a map represents a territory).
2. The sign distorts reality (e.g., fake products resemble but differ from originals).
3. The sign replaces reality (e.g., a simulation feels real but is not).
4. The sign is detached from reality (e.g., virtual reality).

Baudrillard believes that the world of simulation is "transreal and transfinite" and that only a complete collapse can end it, though this remains an unrealized fantasy [2, 206].

Spanish sociologist Manuel Castells has also conducted numerous studies on media technologies and their role in society. His works "The Information Age: Economy, Society, and Culture" [3] are crucial sources on the impact of digital media on the economy and society. British scholars Gunther Kress and Theo van Leeuwen [4], David Gauntlett, Sonia Livingstone of the London School of Economics, and American scholar Henry Jenkins have all made significant contributions to understanding how various forms of audiovisual media (text, image, sound, video) combine to create meaning and their educational and social impacts.

In Uzbekistan, several scholars have studied audiovisual media and their types, contributing to the development of media and communication in the country. For instance, Azamat Inomov has focused on the development of television and video production in Uzbekistan, their societal impact, and their use in education. Gulruxor Tursunova has conducted extensive research on media psychology and communication, exploring the psychological effects of audiovisual media on different audiences, especially youth and children. Farrux Alimov has studied the impact of digital technologies on the media market in Uzbekistan, while Saida Hasanova has researched the effective use of audiovisual media in education, publishing numerous scientific articles.

Results and Discussion. Let's examine the main types of audiovisual media and their applications. These media can be broadly categorized into the following sections:

1. **Films and Videos:**
 - o **Feature Films:** Primarily for entertainment, but also used for educational purposes to depict historical events, literary works, and cultural phenomena.

- **Documentaries:** Aimed at providing information and education, often presenting real events, scientific discoveries, and biographies.

- **Educational Videos:** Include video lectures, courses, trainings, and master classes, used in educational institutions and for independent learning.

2. **Television:**

- **News Programs:** Provide viewers with daily information on events, politics, economy, and culture.

- **Entertainment Programs:** Include TV shows, series, musical and sports broadcasts.

- **Educational Programs:** Designed to educate viewers in various fields, such as science, history, art, and languages.

3. **Presentations:**

- **Business Presentations:** Used in meetings and conferences to showcase products, services, reports, and plans.

- **Educational Presentations:** Help teachers visualize material and make it easier for students to understand.

- **Marketing Presentations:** Attract potential clients and partners, highlighting the advantages and unique features of products or services.

4. **Interactive Media:**

- **Interactive Whiteboards:** Used in schools and universities to make teaching more dynamic and engaging, allowing writing, drawing, and interaction with educational materials.

- **Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR and AR):** Provide users with immersive virtual experiences or add digital elements to the real world, widely used in education, medicine, and entertainment.

5. **Multimedia Programs:**

- **Educational Programs:** Mobile and computer applications that help users learn new subjects and skills.

- **Games:** Besides entertainment, include educational and developmental elements, supporting learning through play.

- **E-books and Journals:** Often include audio and video materials that complement textual information and make it more visual.

6. **Internet Platforms and Social Networks:**

- **YouTube and Vimeo:** Platforms for hosting and watching video content, widely used for education, marketing, and entertainment.

- **Social Networks:** Platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok allow users to share videos and live broadcasts, facilitating information exchange and interaction with the audience.

Jean Baudrillard, in his book "Simulacra and Simulation," presents a more compact division of the above sections into three parts, uniting these components under the term "simulacra" and describing them as examples of this concept. According to Baudrillard's classification:

- **Media and Television:** TV programs, commercials, and movies are vivid examples of simulacra, creating their own images from elements of the real world.

- **Augmented and Virtual Reality:** Virtual games and AR technologies present artificial versions of reality.

- **Social Networks:** Profiles and content on social networks are another example of simulacra, presenting idealized and filtered versions of people and events, distorting reality [2].

Based on the structural characteristics of audiovisual media, they can be optimally classified as follows: 1) Audio Media; 2) Visual Media; 3) Audiovisual Media; 4) Interactive Media; 5) E-books and Multimedia Resources. Let's look at the internal components and explanations of these sections.

1. **Audio Media:** Designed to convey information in audio format, including:
 - **Radio:** Encompasses various radio programs, news, music, and other audio content.
 - **Podcasts:** Internet-distributed audio programs covering various topics.
 - **Audiobooks:** Audio versions of classic and modern literature, scientific works, and other materials.
2. **Visual Media:** Designed to convey information visually, including:
 - **Pictures and Drawings:** Images in newspapers, magazines, and online articles.
 - **Infographics:** Conveying information graphically.
 - **Posters and Banners:** Advertising and informational materials in public places.
3. **Audiovisual Media:** Combining audio and visual components, including:
 - **Television:** Various programs, news, and shows broadcast via TV channels.
 - **Films and Videos:** Movies, series, and short videos in cinemas and online.
 - **Multimedia Presentations:** Multimedia presentations created using PowerPoint and other tools.
 - **Webinars and Online Classes:** Seminars and educational videos conducted online.
4. **Interactive Media:** Designed for user interaction, including:
 - **Virtual Reality (VR):** Creating virtual worlds and interactive experiences.
 - **Augmented Reality (AR):** Adding virtual elements to the real world to create experiences.
 - **Computer Games:** Interactive games with educational and entertainment types.
5. **E-books and Multimedia Resources:** Including:
 - **E-books (eBooks):** Electronic format books containing text and images.
 - **Multimedia Courses:** Educational multimedia courses distributed via CDs, DVDs, or online platforms.

Conclusion. Audiovisual media play an important role in modern life due to their wide range of applications, from education and business to entertainment and social interaction. They offer contemporary elements that can be chosen to achieve various goals and meet the needs of different audiences. The above classification of audiovisual media facilitates their use in various fields and helps provide specific information. Each medium has its own place and advantages, and to use them effectively, it is necessary to understand their internal characteristics and essence.

References

1. Marshall McLuhan. *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man.* – Canada: McGraw-Hill, 1964. – P. 318.

2. Бодрийяр, Ж. Симулякры и симуляции / Ж. Бодрийяр; [пер. с фр. А.Качалова]. – М.: Издательский дом «ПОСТУМ», 2015. – 240 с. – (Технология свободы).
3. Castells, Manuel. The rise of the network society I Manuel Castells. – 2nd ed., with a new pref. p. cm. – (Information age ; v.1). – 2010. – P. 628.
4. Tran, Thuy. (2017). READING IMAGES – THE GRAMMAR OF VISUAL DESIGN. VNU Journal of Foreign Studies. 33. 10.25073/2525-2445/vnufs.4217. Authors: Gunther Kress & Theo van Leeuwen Routledge, 2006.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322105004_READING_IMAGES_-_THE_GRAMMAR_OF_VISUAL_DESIGN
5. Коджаспирова Г.М. Технические средства обучения и методика их использования: учеб. Пособие для студ. высш. учеб. заведений / Г.М.Коджаспирова, К.В.Петров. – 5-е изд., стер. – М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2008. – 352 с.
6. Peters, John Durham. Speaking into the air: a history of the idea of communication / John Durham Peters. Communication-Philosophy-History. I. Title. 1999. – P. 388.
7. Lev Manovich. The Language of New Media. – Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press, 2001. – P. 358.